

Potential of Bivalves for Bioremediation of Wastewater – Comparative Assessment of Biofiltration and Biosorption

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Overview

- *Corbicula fluminea* is an invasive clam species found worldwide.
- Clams can remove contaminants from wastewater through **biofiltration**
- Clam shells may remove contaminants from wastewater through **biosorption**

- Wastewater may contain a wide variety of contaminants, namely pharmaceuticals.

AIM

to evaluate the potential of *Corbicula fluminea*, considering both the living organisms (biofiltration) and the shells (biosorption), in the removal of some of the most frequent contaminants in wastewater.

Methodology

Chemical quantification of the contaminants before and after each treatment (HPLC / electrophoresis)

Ecotoxicological assessment before and after each treatment – microalgae *Raphidocelis subcapitata* growth (OECD 201:2011)

removal efficiency

Results

Conclusions

Living bivalves showed the best performance on removing fluoxetine and diclofenac. Despite they can work for specific wastewaters (where these contaminants dominate), they do not likely represent a broad solution for urban wastewater treatment, also considering maintenance requirements.

Corbicula fluminea pyrolyzed shells represent a potential solution for removal of diclofenac, fluoxetine and metformin from the wastewater.

The high removal efficiency of specific pharmaceuticals, allied to the ecological benefits of removing *C. fluminea* shells from invaded aquatic systems, supports the use of pyrolyzed shells as a promising approach for treatment of urban wastewaters, specially at lower pH values.

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